

5^o CONGRESSO
INTERNACIONAL
SOBRE
AMBIÊNCIAS
5th INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS ON AMBIANCES

**LISBON'S BOOK
OF ABSTRACTS**

**08^{to} 11
OCT
2024**

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PORTUGAL - BRAZIL

**SENSORY
EXPLORATIONS**

AMBIANCES IN A CHANGING WORLD

EDITORIAL

Welcome to the 5th International Congress on Ambiances

Sensory Explorations, Ambiances in a Changing World

In 2024, the 5th International Congress on Ambiances is held from October 8 to 11 in two universities located in two different countries and on two distinct continents: in Lisbon, Portugal, with Lusófona University, and in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, with the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro).

This conference brings together scientific contributions from academics, practitioners, artists, doctoral students and researchers working on architectural and urban ambiances, drawing on multidisciplinary expertise from fields as diverse as anthropology, architecture, landscape, computer science, cultural studies, design, engineering, geography, musicology, psychology, sociology, urban studies, etc. Together they demonstrate the variety of themes and issues in this field of study, presenting the latest research, projects, and methodological approaches.

By focusing on the sensitive quality of spaces, Ambiances create layers of meaning on a conductive scale that eases the apprehension of everyday life, where the cultural and affective dimensions are translatable by the situated bodily experience, on a macroscopic scale, which intersects diverse cultures, rhythms and knowledge.

The study of Urban Ambiances has shown that the practical, experimental and relational nature of human-urban coexistence is one of the possible ways to overcome the dichotomies and fragilities posed by current dilemmas, such as the difficulty of urban mobility in various metropolises, social asymmetries, territorial conflicts at local level or the lack of public spaces enabling the satisfactory development of everyday life. At the same time, research into ambiances opens different possibilities for rethinking the way we occupy the world, because ambiances are agents that enable associative forms of sharing public spaces: they intensify social relations and make convivial relations less discordant.

After the Congresses in Grenoble (Creating an Atmosphere, 2008), Montreal (Ambiances in Action, 2012), Volos (Ambiances, Tomorrow: The Future of Ambiances, 2016), and the online 4th edition (Ambiances, Alloaesthesia: Senses, Inventions, Worlds, 2020), this 5th edition explores the sensory aspects of ambiances in a changing world.

In its fifth quadrennial congress, the objective is to outline the state of new conceptual, methodological, and practical issues in relation to architectural and urban ambiances. The focus will be open to the contemporary themes of our scientific community, but it also also wishes to welcome and work on new sensory exploration in a world in constant transformation.

The aim is to examine how contemporary environmental, social, technological, political, and ethical changes can interact with sensitive worlds, their environments, bodies, senses, and the ways in which people experience them. The Congress on Ambiances aims to foster a "barn of discussions" on experiences, based on themes that highlight sensitivity and the cultural landscape, urban and micro-urban politics, local arts and interventions, the body and the senses, design strategies, adaptation processes, among others.

Mohammed Boubezari
Cristiane Rose Duarte
Ethel Pinheiro

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The congress is organised by Lusófona University in Lisbon, The Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro) in Rio de Janeiro with the help of the International Ambiances Network, Scientific and Thematic Network of the French Ministry of Culture.

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- Grenoble School of Higher Studies in Architecture,
- AAU "Ambiances, Architectures, Urbanités", Joint research unit between CNRS (French National Centre for Scientific Research), Grenoble School of Architecture, Nantes School of Architecture, Centrale Nantes,
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- Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico, Brazil,
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- DAU - TerrA.ID, Unidade de Investigação e Desenvolvimento (I&D) do Departamento de Arquitetura e Urbanismo, Lisboa.
- SPARC - Sensory Places in Architecture.

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L05

ATTUNING WITH THE WORLD: IMAGINING AND MAKING ATMOSPHERES

CHAIRS Aleksandar Staničić
Shanti Sumartojo

The relationship between atmospheres, imagination, and architectural design is a complex one. While the built environment is often described, experienced or recalled as atmospheric, we contend that we need new methods of imagination in architectural and design practice - and in particular through making - to advance design for and with atmospheres.

One reason for this is that imaginative processes of making are powerful in helping people feel their way into atmospheres, by engaging directly with materials and their affordances, by working collaboratively with other people and non-humans, and by engaging in complex manual problem solving that requires people to attend carefully to the actual, situated conditions of their practice. Moreover, architectural methods of visualising, drawing and modelling are intended to support design processes that focus on the structure itself more than the experience of those who might one day encounter it. Such processes necessarily reduce the built environment to flattened and abstracted propositions. While these may be imagined as atmospheric by the architect or designer, if, as Edensor and Sumartojo (2015) insist, atmospheres cannot be designed, then how can we actually develop an atmospheric attunement with the world? How might we develop an atmospheric praxis - a possibility that brings a deep conceptual engagement with the past decade of thinking about atmospheres together with the expertise and methodological rigor of architectural practice? In this panel we invite submissions that discuss new methods for designing with, through or for atmospheres. We hope to hear from both creative practitioners who work with a concept of atmospheres in the built environment, and researchers who consider imagining or making built

environments. In particular, we wish to focus on:

New approaches to methods of imagination or design - how can we speculate about built futures atmospherically? What does an atmospheric lens or practice make possible?

How can architecture's role as a means by which culture is produced, reinforced and challenged be approached through an atmospheric lens.

How can we attend to and account for sensory aspects - light, sound, touch, temperature, the movement of air, proprioception and more - achieved through various architectural elements?

MEMORIES AND ATMOSPHERES: LEARNING FROM THE PAMMATONE COMPLEX IN GENOA

MEMÓRIAS E ATMOSFERAS: APRENDENDO COM O COMPLEXO PAMMATONE EM GÊNNOVA

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ABSTRACT

We need memories to co-generate affective atmospheres, which are unique to the extent that they develop from analogies with other experiences. The greatest atmospheric engagement occurs in spaces resonating with our embodied habits, emotional affinities, and body memories. This paper investigates strategies that make a space memorable and observes how memories trigger the atmospheric potential of certain places. Our case study is the Pammatone business and housing complex designed by Franco Albini and Franca Helg in the Piccapietra district in Genoa in the mid-20th century. We purposely selected a building that resulted from an enduring atmospheric praxis rather than an attempt to induce sensorial oversaturation: Albini and Helg were pioneers in teaching how to stage atmospheric spaces—long before the current “atmospheric turn.”

KEYWORDS: memory. atmosphere. co-generation. Albini Helg. Pammatone

RESUMO

Precisamos de memórias para co-gerar atmosferas afetivas, sempre únicas na medida em que crescem em analogias com outras experiências. O êxtase atmosférico mais forte envolve espaços que ressoam com nossos hábitos incorporados, afinidades emocionais e memórias corporais. Este artigo investiga estratégias para tornar um espaço memorável e observa como as memórias ativam o potencial atmosférico de alguns lugares. Nosso estudo de caso é o complexo empresarial e habitacional Pammatone projetado por Franco Albini e Franca Helg no distrito de Piccapietra, em Gênova, em meados do século XX. Selecionamos propositalmente um edifício que não induz uma supersaturação sensorial, mas resulta de uma práxis atmosférica duradoura: Albini e Helg foram pioneiros em ensinar como encenar espaços atmosféricos—muito antes da atual “virada atmosférica”.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: memória. atmosfera. co-geração. Albini Helg. Pammatone

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